

The Impact of Supplementary Services on Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty: A Study on Menoufia University Hospitals

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Abstract:

This paper attempts to identify the role of Supplementary Services (SS) in affecting Customer Satisfaction (CS) and Customer Loyalty (CL) at Menoufia University hospitals (MUH). The research community is composed of all employees at MUH (University Hospitals, National Liver Institute and Students Hospitals) in Egypt. Using Lovelock, 1992; 1995 for measuring SS, Athanassopoulos, et al., 2001 for measuring CS and Parasuraman, 1996 for measuring CL. About 338 survey questionnaires were distributed. Multiple follow-ups yielded 275 statistically usable questionnaires. Survey responses were 81%.

The research discovered a number of results which are (1) there is a positive relationship between SS, CS, and CL at MUH. In other words, increasing the level of SS leads to improved CS and CL. The positive impact of SS will encourage customers to be satisfied and loyal. In other words, SS is an important indicator of CS and CL, (2) the results of the analysis showed that hospitals in MUH, which increases the level of SS, it reflects positively on CS and CL. In other words, SS is a key factor for CS and CL, (3) the results of the analysis showed that SS has a significant impact on CS and CL at MUH. SS is an important tool for organizations to increase their income and market share, and (4) the researcher used CFA in order to verify the quality of the various research measures. It is clear that all the statement of SS, CS, and CL are greater than 0.50, which corresponds to the GFI. This is a good indicator of all other statistical analysis. In addition to that, the researcher depends on SEM because it is one of the best ways to use the multivariable test. SEM has been used to test the compatibility model using AMOS analysis. In order to ascertain whether the model is compatible with the sample data used. Also, it already measures the variable that should be measured. In general, it is clear that the previous indicators are good for making all other statistical analysis.

The study referred to a number of recommendations which are: (1) MUH Department should raise awareness among its staff of the difference between SS, and basic service, (2) the management of MUH should be interested in the quality of the service that can occur through the quality control department, (3) It is recommended to increase the hospitality level within in MUH and provide more effective solutions for patients where the person is expected to be shipped mainly according to the service received, (4) The feedback of agents must be taken into account, using questionnaires, commercial research studies, and specialists. The aim is to be reassured regarding the quality of services, (5) customer services require much experience. This may be attained via training programs for workers responsible for services, (6) Business processes must be smooth, while the time for service should be kept at a minimum. To realize this all staff need motivation and empowerment to perform their quality, and (7) MUH in Egypt should know that the customer should be respected, and staff should try to obtain information, suggestions or problems in order to improve service delivery and CS.

1. Introduction

The concept of service has been studied by many researchers during the last few years. There are many indicators that have collected the idea of service, quality, and satisfaction with the services provided (Lewis & Mitchell, 1990).

There are two types of services, the first is the basic service and refers to the results of the purchase of a particular item expected by the customer for a fee paid. The second is SS and refers to a set of services that facilitate the use of basic services (Lovelock & Wirtz, 2016).

There are two types of services. They are basic service, and SS. Essential service is the goods that satisfy the desires and needs of customers. These products are augmented by SS. It facilitates the use of basic services and enhances their attractiveness and value (Storey & Easingwood, 1998; Bitner et al., 2000).

SS are classified into two types. The first is concerned with the promotion of SS and the second concerns the facilitation of SS. SS include security, consultation, expectations, and hospitality. The facilitation of additional services includes payment, invoices, requests, and information. These elements

facilitate the use of the underlying product and enhance service delivery. These elements also help distinguish competitors (Lovlock et al., 2009).

CL will increase when CS is achieved. CL will decrease if the level of satisfaction drops to a certain point. Customers who are satisfied tend to be more loyal than satisfied. There is a positive relationship between CS and CL. CL leads to an increase in organization profitability (Chi 2005).

CS and CL are a top priority for the success of organization and profitability. CS does not cause CL (Arantola 2000).

The client is a link to business success. CS and CL should be integrated into the enterprise's long-term goal. CS is a key element of any organization wishing to increase CL (Dick & Basu 1994, Oliva et al., 1992).

2. Supplementary Services

SS create a difference between a successful and another unsuccessful company. Additional services affect customer value by enhancing its attractiveness, enabling the company to impose a higher price (Levitt, 1980).

SS can be classified into two types of services. They are supporting products or services on the one hand and facilitating services on the other. The first type of service is additional products or services that enable the company to distinguish its products from competitors. The second type of service is products or services that facilitate the use of basic services and enhance their attractiveness and value (Lovlock, 1992; 1995, Kotler et al., 2010).

SS can be classified into eight groups: information, order taking, consulting, hospitality, safekeeping, exceptions, billing, and payment (Lovlock, 1992; 1995; Naipaul & Parsa, 2000; Goyal, 2004; Hume, 2008; Lovelock et al., 2011).

- 1. Information about Service (IS):** It is an additional service that customers need to provide services. IS provides guidance and understanding to use the correct core products. The client may ask about how to obtain the service or product.
- 2. Order Taking (OT):** It is an SS, and the process of receipt of applications must be accurate and quick to enable the client to undertake any unnecessary physical or mental effort. Companies are interested in potential customers, and this requires collecting customer-related IS so that they can satisfy their needs and desires.
- 3. Provide Consultancy (PC):** It is an SS. Service is improved by making them more attractive to customers. These services include specialized counseling and advice. Consulting tailored to customer needs adds value to the services and goods offered by the company.
- 4. Good Hospitality (GH):** This is SS promotion. Service delivery is improved by adding value to products or services and making them more attractive to customers. Hospitality is linked to services that bring happiness to old customers and must be designed to acquire new customers. Hospitality starts at the service site, including drinks, security, toilets, waiting facilities and amenities, sitting areas, lounges, parking spaces, security, transportation, entertainment, newspapers, and magazines. The quality of the company's hospitality services may reduce or increase CS with its core services or products.
- 5. Safe Keeping (SK):** It is an SS interested in maintaining customer records and must take into account the security, privacy, and confidentiality of customers. SK is an SS that provides services by adding value to the products or services of the organization. The organization must take care of the client's personal property. SK services include the care of goods purchased by customers and the care of customers' property for goods purchased. Customer care includes baggage handling, childcare, parking, security personnel, safety deposit boxes, and coat rooms.
- 6. Provide Exceptions (PE):** It enables staff to respond effectively and quickly. Special requests are made by customers who wish to leave many of the company's normal operating procedures. Pre-requisites may be made for personal needs. Problems arise due to product failure or smooth service delivery. This may occur due to equipment failure, delays, accidents, or customers facing challenges in using the service or product. The company must make suggestions for improvement or dissatisfaction. Customers are compensated for the failure of the company.
- 7. Issuing Billing (IB):** Billings are a common supplemental service in all paid private services. It must be accurate and understandable to customers. The incomplete or inaccurate invoice may affect CS with the

service, such as handwritten invoices. Invoices may cause customer difficulty in obtaining service, as customers expect clear and informative invoices — unread and unreadable printing results in poor customer experience. Companies should focus on designing invoices based on what customers want.

8. Payment Methods (PM): Payment/Invoices are an SS that customers need, as customers want to know what they pay for. Customers can pay more if they enjoy a simple and respectful treatment, as customers expect a convenient way to pay their bills. There are many ways to pay such as payment of debit and credit cards, and this requires customers to insert cards, coins or banknotes into the machines. Some payments are still made by checks to cash hand. Using credit cards is the most common payment method used by customers.

3. Customers Satisfaction

Consumer behavior refers to the choice of goods and services to meet their basic needs. Product quality, price, service, consumer sentiment, personal factors, and situational factors are some of the factors that affect CS (Hague & Hague 2016).

CS can provide benefits for the organization such as CL. When a customer is satisfied, he can make the customer buy products or services frequently and recommend them to potential customers. It is impossible to grow the organization in case the if it ignores customer needs (Tao 2014).

The organization should maintain the customer. If competitors improve CS, they lose corporate customers. While improving CS, we should note customer expectations. Quality of service has a direct positive impact on CS. If employees have a positive impact, they can play a big role in increasing CS (Lovelock & Wright, 2007).

CS is very important for business strategy as well as retaining customers and repurchasing the product. To maximize CS, companies must sell their ideas and methods after completing all the necessary documents (Hill et al., 2007).

CS has been a central concept in marketing literature. Today, companies face the strongest competition, because they move from product philosophy to marketing philosophy (Kotler, 2006).

Although CS is an important part of the business, however, satisfaction alone cannot take the business to a higher level. CS results in a positive financial outcome, (Griffin 2002).

CS is measured in terms of satisfaction with the proceedings (SP), satisfaction with the employees (SE), and satisfaction with the services (SS) of the organization. The dimensions of CS are as follows (Athanasopoulos et al., 2001):

- 1. Satisfaction with the progress of the procedures (SP):** The facilities that characterize the hospital, such as its design, location, number of branches, ease of communication, and explanatory signs for the activities of the hospital. SP such as the internal design of the hospital facilitates smooth flow of transactions, there is more than one hospital branch to meet your need, the hospital offers special facilities, the hospital does not make mistakes when it tells me about the progress of my health, the clarity of the signs of the facilities and offices in the hospital, and it is easy to contact the hospital by telephone and via e-mail.
- 2. Satisfaction with the Employees (SE):** The degree of satisfaction of the patient about the hospital staff for their good treatment and behavior and their cooperation in providing services to him. SE such as the hospital staff is characterized by elegance, the staff in the hospital are polite, and their treatment is unique and distinguished with the patient, hospital staff are well aware of the activities and work of the hospital, hospital staff have the knowledge to serve you immediately, hospital staff work freely with me when I have a problem to solve, and employees in the hospital do not hesitate to find the time necessary to provide the best service to the patient.
- 3. Satisfaction with the services of the hospital (SS):** It reflects the view of the general satisfaction of the patient about the services provided to him in terms of multiplicity and rapid submission and solving problems that may face. SS such as the hospital deserves trust, you do not need to have multiple visits to your hospital to solve a specific problem, if there is a problem, the hospital will be willing to discuss this with me, the hospital provides services to patients in secret, good relations between staff and hospital management contribute to better patient service, and the hospital offers a wide variety of services to meet your needs.

4. Customer Loyalty

CL is expressed through Emotional Loyalty (EL) and Behavioral Loyalty (BL). Emotional loyalty is supposed to be a customer recognized and very comfortable for the emergence of belief, behavior, and impression of the institution. In addition, CL to behavior is expressed through the frequent purchase behavior of a company's product or service. CL will encourage you to buy and think before changing their mind to buy other services. CL is built through sourcing and design decisions. Design for CL requires a customer-centric approach that recognizes the desires and future of the service. CL was built over time through multiple transactions (Thomas & Tobe, 2013).

CL is the behavior while CS is the attitude. Therefore, there are certain differences between factors that affect CS and CL (Gajjar 2013).

CL cannot be reached until customers feel satisfied with their products and services. Customer behavior towards specific goods and services is the most important. If customer behaves positively, they will be considered a loyal customer (Abdullah, 2012).

CL is another important factor in CS. The relationship between CS and was the most popular subject in marketing theory. Therefore, many studies have shown that CS and CL are directly related to one another. CS are CL and unsatisfied patients (Heskett et al., 2011).

CL was a subject of great interest in both academia and practice; the rule was also found to be beneficial to the company. Companies practice competition in most sectors, and this means customer commitment. Customers favor more annual profits (Michael et al., 2008).

The quality of the different product or service has its impact on CL. Customers get emotionally influenced by them. Thus, CS is not the same as CL (Dickie, 2008).

Corporate growth and performance are based on CL, repetitive actions being crucial, too. Repeated buying a product or service assures loyalty. Future products or services will be bought, accordingly (Kotler, 2006).

Trust is another fundament of CL. Second, there should a higher value than that of competitors. Third, if this is attained, high emotional attachment will be realized (Kumar & Shah, 2004; Pitta et al., 2006).

CL means frequent purchase behavior based on a personal preference for a particular product or service. CL is the most competitive feature of the organization. CL is seen as the strength of the relationship between the relative position of the individual and the re-care (Griffin 2002).

CL is more complex than in previous years. This is due to technological breakthroughs and widespread use of the Internet. CL requires to focus the value of its products and services and demonstrate its interest in CS (Griffin 2002).

The customer represents actual loyalty to the purchase of different products or services from the same organization that should consider the possibility is choosing a long-term brand (Feick et al., 2001).

There are two types of CL. They are BL and EL. BL refers to frequent shopping in a particular retailer. EL refers to the concerns of the customer about a particular retailer based on their previous buying experience and position. In both BL and EL, increasing CS should increase CL. When customers are dissatisfied, customers can express their complaints to the competitor (Reichheld & Schefter 2000). EL is achieved when the customer feels that the brand is in line with its value (Gremmler & Brown, 1999).

CL is measured in terms of verbal communication (VC), the intention of the spoken word (IS), sensitivity to price (SP), and the behavior of the complaint (BC). The dimensions of CL are as follows (Zeithaml et al., 1996):

- 1. Verbal Communication (VC):** It means that the patient promotes the services of the hospital through positive speech, and recommends the services of the hospital, as well as encouraging friends and acquaintances to the services of the hospital. VC such as I often say positive things about hospital services provided to other people, I always recommend hospital services to anyone who asks for my advice, and I encourage my friends, acquaintances, and relatives to deal with the services provided by the hospital.
- 2. The Intention of the Spoken Word (IS):** It expresses the patient's opinion before the knowledge and friends by mentioning the positives of the hospital which lead to the promotion of the hospital, IS such as I consider that the hospital services provided are optional first, I intend to deal better with the services of the hospital in the coming period, I am expected to continue my follow-up of hospital services for the coming period, and I intend to hesitate to this hospital during the coming period.

3. **Price Sensitivity (SP):** It represents the patient's willingness to pay a higher price for hospital services and not to switch to competing hospitals for lower prices. SP such as I will pay any price requested for the services provided by the hospital even if the prices of other hospitals are lower, I will not deal with any competitor hospital offering lower prices, Low prices in competitive hospitals will not lead me to switch to them, and the price is not important to me when dealing with this hospital.
4. **The Behavior of the Complaint (BC):** It represents the patient's reaction to the problem that may get him through his treatment with the hospital and work to resolve and not published to patients or hospitals competing. BC such as I will not switch to any competitor hospital if I have a problem dealing with this hospital, if I have a problem dealing with this hospital I will not transfer my complaint to patients close to me, and if I have a problem with the service provided by the hospital, I will transfer it directly to the employees in order to solve it.

5. Research Model

The research model suggests that SS (independent variable) has an effect on CS and CL (dependent variable). SS is measured in terms of IS, OT, PC, GH, SK, PE, IB, and PM (Lovelock, 1992; 1995). CS is measured in terms of SP, SE, and SS (Athanasopoulos et al., 2001). CL is measured in terms of VC, IS, SP, and BC (Parasuraman, 1996).

Figure (1)
The Research Model

6. Research Questions

The researcher reached to the research problem through two sources. The first is the previous studies that dealt with the relationship between SS, CS, and CL at MUH. This called for the researcher to test this relationship in the Egyptian environment.

The second is the pilot study, which was conducted in an interview with (30) employees at MUH. The researcher found several indicators explain the importance of SS in affecting CS and CL. The research questions are as follows:

Q1: What is the nature and extent of the relationship between supplementary services and customer satisfaction at Menoufia University hospitals?

Q2: What is the extent of the relationship between supplementary services and customer loyalty at Menoufia University hospitals?

7. Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were developed to test if there is a significant correlation between SS, CS, and CL

H1: Supplementary services has no statistically significant effect on customer satisfaction at Menoufia University hospitals.

H2: There is no relationship between Supplementary services and customer loyalty at Menoufia University hospitals.

8. Population and Sample

The research population included 3307 employees in MUH. The stratified random sample was used to collect primary data from the different categories of employees. The following equation specifies the size of the sample (Daniel, 1999):

$$n = \frac{N \times (Z)^2 \times P(1-P)}{d^2(N-1) + (Z)^2 \times P(1-P)}$$

The number of samples obtained by 344 employees at MUH is presented in the following table.

Table (1) Distribution of the Sample Size on the Population

Job Category	Number	Percentage	Size of Sample
Physicians	488	15%	344X 15% = 52
Nurses	2141	65%	344 X 65% = 224
Administrative Staff	678	20%	344 X 20% = 68
Total	3307	100%	344 X 100% = 344

Source: Personnel Department at Menoufia University, 2018

Table (2) Characteristics of Items of the Sample

Dimorphic Variables	Number	Percentage	
1- Job Title	Physicians	100	33%
	Nurses	150	50%
	Administrative	50	17%
	Total	300	100%
2- Gender	Male	230	76%
	Female	70	24%
	Total	300	100%
3- Marital Status	Single	130	43%
	Married	170	57%
	Total	300	100%
4- Age	Under 30	100	33%
	From 30 to 45	125	42%
	Above 45	75	25%
	Total	300	100%
5- Educational Level	University	175	58%
	Post Graduate	125	42%
	Total	300	100%
6- Period of Experience	Less than 5 years	50	17%
	From 5 to 10	200	66%
	More than 10	50	17%
	Total	300	100%

9. The Survey Structure

The survey used to measure SS, CS, and CL at SCU. This survey consists of three parts. The first described the objectives of the research by asking the respondents to participate in the survey. The second

asked for the respondents’ demographic variable such as gender, academic degree, marital status, age, and period of experience. The third presented the questions related to SS, CS, and CL at SCU.

About 344 questionnaires were distributed. 300 usable questionnaires. The response rate was 87%.

The research depends on the Likert scale for each statement ranging from (5) “full agreement,” (4) for “agree,” (3) for “neutral,” (2) for “disagree,” and (1) for “full disagreement.”

10. Research Variables and Methods of Measuring

Table (3)
Description and Measuring of the Research Variables

Main Variables		Sub-Variables	Number of Statement	Methods of Measuring Variables	
Independent Variable	SS	IS	7	Lovelock, 1992; 1995	
		OT	6		
		PC	5		
		GH	5		
		SK	5		
		PE	6		
		IB	4		
		PM	5		
	Total	43			
Dependent Variable	CS	SP	6	Athanassopoulos, et al, 2001	
		SE	6		
		SS	6		
		Total	18		
	CL	VC	3	Parasuraman, 1996	
		IS	4		
		SP	4		
		BC	3		
			Total		14

11. Data Analysis and Testing Hypotheses

The researcher has employed the following methods: (1) Cronbach's alpha or ACC, (2) Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA), and (3) F- test and T-test. All these tests are found in SPSS.

12. Hypotheses Testing

Before testing the hypotheses and research questions, descriptive statistics were performed to find out means and standard deviations of SS, CS, and CL.

Table (4): shows the mean and standard deviations of SS, CS, and CL

Variables	The Dimension	Mean	Standard Deviation
SS	IS	4.03	0.631
	OT	4.17	0.748
	PC	4.15	0.803
	GH	4.05	1.04
	SK	3.95	0.995
	PE	4.20	0.759
	IB	4.07	0.687
	PM	3.93	0.701
	Total Measurement	4.07	0.600
CS	SP	4.30	0.672
	SE	2.93	1.12
	SS	3.45	0.972
	Total Measurement	3.56	0.618
CL	VC	4.30	0.672
	IS	2.94	1.13
	SP	3.46	0.983
	BC	3.92	1.05
	Total Measurement	3.59	0.645

Source: SPSS, V.23, 2015

Table (4), presented the various facets of SS, CS, and CL. Most of the respondents identified the presence of SS ($M=4.07$, $SD=0.600$) and CS ($M=3.56$, $SD=0.618$) and CL ($M=3.59$, $SD=0.645$).

12.1. Evaluating Reliability

Table (5): Reliability of SS, CS, and CL

Variables	Dimension	Number of Statement	ACC
SS	IS	7	0.827
	OT	6	0.901
	PC	5	0.854
	GH	5	0.941
	SK	5	0.919
	PE	6	0.903
	IB	4	0.788
	PM	5	0.700
	Total Measurement	43	0.958
CS	SP	6	0.920
	SE	6	0.995
	SS	6	0.949
	Total Measurement	18	0.899
CL	VC	3	0.799
	IS	4	0.992
	SP	4	0.920
	BC	3	0.962
	Total Measurement	14	0.872

Source: SPSS, V.23, 2015

Table (5) presents the reliability of SS, CS, and CL. SS is reliable because the ACC is 0.958. CS is reliable because the ACC is 0.899. CL is reliable because the ACC is 0.872.

Accordingly, three scales were defined, SS (43 variables), where ACC represented about 0.955, CS (18 variables), where ACC represented 0.942 and CL (14 variables), where ACC represented 0.942.

12.2. The Means, St. Deviations, and Correlation among Variables

Table (6): Means, Standard Deviations and Intercorrelations among Variables

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	SS	CS	CL
SS	4.07	0.600	1		
CS	3.56	0.618	0.624 **	1	
CL	3.59	0.645	0.631 **	0.956 **	1

Source: SPSS, V.23, 2015

Regarding Table (6), the level of SS is high (Mean=4.07; SD=0.600), while CS is (Mean=3.56; SD=0.618). and CL is (Mean=3.59; SD=0.645).The overall correlation between SS and CS is 0.624. Also, the correlation between SS and CL is 631.

12.3. The Correlation between SS, CS, and CL

Table (7): Correlation Matrix between SS, CS and CL

Research Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
SS	IS	1									
	OT	0.31	1								
	PC	0.25	0.84	1							
	GH	0.41	0.44	0.41	1						
	SK	0.34	0.45	0.42	0.89	1					
	PE	0.26	0.99	0.83	0.42	0.44	1				
	IB	0.92	0.30	0.24	0.45	0.37	0.24	1			
	PM	0.78	0.42	0.37	0.67	0.74	0.38	0.64	1		
Total	0.66	0.80	0.73	0.80	0.79	0.77	0.65	0.81	1		
CS	0.48	0.53	0.44	0.50	0.39	0.50	0.46	0.47	0.62	1	
CL	0.39	0.59	0.49	0.50	0.41	0.58	0.37	0.44	0.63	0.95	1

Note: ** Correlation is significant at 0.01 level

Source: SPSS, V.23, 2015

Based on the Table (7), a correlation matrix between SS (IS, OT, PC, GH, SK, PE, IB, and PM) and CS and CL.

12.4. Supplementary Services and Customer Satisfaction

The relationship between SS and CS is determined. The first hypothesis to be tested is:

H1: There is no relationship between supplementary services and customer satisfaction at Menoufia University Hospitals.

Table (8): MRA Results for SS and CS

The Variables of SS	Beta	R	R ²
1. IS	0.126	0.483	0.233
2. OT	0.826*	0.530	0.280
3. PC	0.053	0.441	0.194
4. GH	0.623**	0.500	0.250
5. SK	0.600*	0.397	0.157
6. PE	0.406	0.502	0.252
7. IB	0.197	0.468	0.219
8. PM	0.309	0.478	0.228
▪ MCC		0.680	
▪ DC		0.463	
▪ CF		31.343	
▪ FD		8,291	
▪ IF		2.51	
** P < .01			

Source: SPSS, V.23, 2015

As Table (8) proves that there is a relationship between SS and CS, it represents 68%, according to MCC. Also, SS may interpret about 46% according to DC. Therefore, it was decided to refuse the null hypothesis which states that there is no statistically significant impact of SS on CS. The alternative hypothesis has been accepted because MRA had shown that there was a relationship at a statistical significance level of 0.01 (according to F-Test) between SS and CS according to T-test.

12.5. Supplementary Services and Customer Loyalty

The relationship between SS and CL is determined. The second hypothesis to be tested is:

H2: Supplementary services has no significant effect on customer loyalty at Menoufia University Hospitals.

Table (9) MRA Results for SS and CL

The Variables of SS	Beta	R	R ²
1. IS	0.086	0.393	0.154
2. OT	0.658*	0.598	0.357
3. PC	0.075	0.493	0.243
4. GH	0.539**	0.500	0.250
5. SK	0.389	0.418	0.174
6. PE	0.127	0.581	0.337
7. IB	0.030	0.371	0.137
8. PM	0.122	0.441	0.194
▪ MCC		0.683	
▪ DC		0.466	
▪ CF		31.756	
▪ FD		8,291	
▪ IF		2.51	
** P < .01			

Source: SPSS, V.23, 2015

As Table (9) proves that there is a relationship between SS and CL, it represents 68%, according to MCC. Also, SS may interpret about 46% according to DC. Therefore, it was decided to refuse the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis because MRA had shown that there was a relationship at a statistical significance level of 0.01 (according to F-Test) between SS and CL according to T-test.

13. Research Results

1. There is a positive relationship between SS, CS, and CL at MUH. In other words, increasing the level of SS leads to improved CS and CL. The positive impact of SS will encourage customers to be satisfied and loyal. In other words, SS is an important indicator of CS and CL
2. The results of the analysis showed that hospitals in MUH, which increases the level of SS, it reflects positively on CS and CL. In other words, SS is a key factor for CS and CL.
3. The results of the analysis showed that SS has a significant impact on CS and CL at MUH. SS is an important tool for organizations to increase their income and market share.
4. The researcher used CFA in order to verify the quality of the various research measures. It is clear that all the statement of SS, CS, and CL are greater than 0.50, which corresponds to the GFI. This is a good indicator of all other statistical analysis. In addition to that, the researcher depends on SEM because it is one of the best ways to use the multivariable test. SEM has been used to test the compatibility model using AMOS analysis. In order to ascertain whether the model is compatible with the sample data used. Also, it already measures the variable that should be measured. In general, it is clear that the previous indicators are good for making all other statistical analysis.

14. Recommendations

1. MUH management should raise awareness among its employees of the difference between SS and basic service.
2. MUH management should raise awareness among its staff about the difference between SS and basic service and how each one of them is important in its own way.
3. The MUH management should be concerned with the quality of service that can occur through awareness that can be disseminated through the quality control department.
4. MUH should increase the level of good hospitality to provide more effective payment solutions for patients and their families.
5. MUH should pay great attention to customer services by selecting skilled workers on how to provide service and gain customer services and design a training program for them to provide them with the knowledge and skills needed to provide services.
6. MUH in Egypt respect of customers is a must. IS and suggestions must be heeded for better service and CS.
7. MUH should maintain the existing customers for their satisfaction. This is because the cost of maintaining the current customer is less as a reason for a new customer and to keep it longer. The customer acquires a sense of loyalty to the organization, and therefore works to strengthen it and acquire new clients.
8. MUH should adopt the service quality strategy in which everyone wins, through which they provide value to customers, and customers remain loyal to the organization. The value provided must be in mind CS.
9. Factors that promote CS are crucial. Hence, data regarding expectations and recommendations for improving the service quality level must be made available. CS will ensure customers' loyalty to the organization. It is a marketing mechanism attracting customers.
10. Modern methods to provide quality services must be available. This may be through relationship management methods. These methods ensure the stronger relationship with the customer. Service quality has a strong impact on CS. Therefore, a strategy that aims to enhance customer service and CL must heed these issues. Important determinants of CL surely include service quality before other factors. Therefore, service quality premium of a given organization is paramount. Therefore, the provision of service quality premium should be the objective of the organization's business strategy.
11. A competitive advantage distinguishing the products and services of the organization is needed. High quality services are of utmost importance for the organization to attain competitive advantage. In other words, innovating services is critical. Customers must be the focus of each strategy. MUH in Egypt should consider the final result of their inventions in the quality department.

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